

ANALYSIS OF THE HOUSING PRICE BUBBLE INDEX AND SUB-INDICES IN UZBEKISTAN**Berdaliyeva Mukhabbatkhan***PhD student,**Scientific research center "Scientific bases and problems of the development of the economy of Uzbekistan"
under the Tashkent state university of economics***Abstract**

This study analyzes the housing price bubble index and its sub-indices in Uzbekistan, a developing country with a rapidly growing real estate market. The research aims to identify potential housing price bubbles and their key drivers in Uzbekistan's specific context.

The study was conducted using extensive data on various economic indicators related to the housing market, including housing prices, construction costs, interest rates and income levels. By analyzing the housing price bubble index and its sub-indices, the study provides a clear understanding of the factors contributing to potential price deviations from fundamental values.

The findings of this study will be crucial for policymakers, investors, and homebuyers in Uzbekistan. By understanding the dynamics of housing price bubbles, stakeholders can make more informed decisions regarding housing policies, investment strategies, and homeownership choices. This research is a scholarly resource on housing market dynamics in developing countries and provides valuable insights into the unique challenges and opportunities presented by Uzbekistan's emerging real estate sector.

Keywords: housing finance, price, bubble index, sub-indices, fundamental factors, economic factors, subsidies, investment, construction costs, interest rates, income levels.

Introduction

Housing markets play a crucial role in economic stability and growth, serving as both a significant investment asset and a primary consumption good for households. However, rapid price fluctuations in housing markets, particularly the emergence of price bubbles, can have detrimental effects on macroeconomic stability, potentially leading to financial crises and economic downturns. Understanding the dynamics of housing price bubbles and identifying their early warning signs is therefore crucial for policymakers, investors, and potential homebuyers [8].

Uzbekistan, a developing country in Central Asia, has experienced significant economic growth in recent years, accompanied by a rapidly developing real estate market. This growth is driven by factors such as increasing urbanization, rising incomes, and government policies aimed at promoting homeownership. Recognizing the importance of housing finance in ensuring socio-economic stability, Uzbekistan has implemented policies to make housing more accessible. These include subsidizing initial mortgage payments for citizens and supporting investments in construction companies. As a result, the construction sector contributed 6.3% to the country's gross domestic product in 2023. Furthermore, between 2020 and 2023, government subsidies for initial mortgage contributions have helped approximately 35,300 low-income citizens access new housing.

Despite these positive developments, a significant challenge remains: high housing prices, particularly in central cities. This is primarily attributed to the population's tendency to view real estate as a high-yield investment, further fueling demand and price increases [12]. Addressing this issue requires a multi-faceted approach. Offering the population alternative, attractive investment projects could divert capital away from the real estate market. Simultaneously, measures to increase financial literacy can empower individuals to

make more informed investment decisions beyond real estate, fostering a more balanced investment landscape[1].

This study conducts a comprehensive analysis of the housing price bubble index and its sub-indices in Uzbekistan. The research aims to identify potential housing price bubbles and their key drivers in the context of Uzbekistan's specific economic and institutional environment, including the government's active role in the housing market. By examining a range of economic indicators related to the housing market, including housing prices, construction costs, interest rates, and income levels, the study provides a nuanced understanding of the factors contributing to potential price deviations from fundamental values.

The findings of this study have important implications for various stakeholders in Uzbekistan's housing market. For policymakers, the research highlights the need for effective macroeconomic policies and housing market regulations to mitigate the risks associated with housing price bubbles, while also considering the impact of existing housing programs. Investors can utilize the insights gained from this study to make more informed investment decisions, while potential homebuyers can gain a better understanding of market dynamics and potential risks associated with homeownership. Moreover, this research contributes to the growing body of literature on housing market dynamics in emerging economies, providing valuable insights into the specific challenges and opportunities presented by Uzbekistan's evolving real estate sector.

Methods and materials

In this paper, the housing price bubble index and its sub-indices are analyzed with a multi-faceted methodological approach. The research relies on an extensive review of the theoretical underpinnings of housing finance, by interpreting a wide range of relevant scientific publications.

The methodology is included in a balanced way, with quantitative and qualitative methods—scientific observation, comparative and trend analysis, factor and structural analysis, and statistical, economic, and financial analysis. It allows for a specific understanding of those complicated forces of dynamics driving housing prices in Uzbekistan.

Research on housing finance, especially in the aftermath of financial crises, has been commanding much attention among researchers from every nook and corner of the world. A wide range of literature has cropped up dealing with various dimensions of housing markets and price bubbles, as well as policies recommended or put into place to effect intervention in those markets.

However, other research is dedicated to general house market processes. For instance, Timothy Akinwande and Eddie C.M. Hui [11] provide an elaborate value-chain explanation of housing supply in urban contexts marked by complexities and challenges that guarantee affordability within the same. P. Smets [10] provides a helpful review of housing policies in developing countries themselves, noted that the search for a context-specific approach has become imperative when dealing with housing affordability.

Brueggeman and Fisher [6] discuss in minute detail the aspects of real estate finance and investment profitability to guide investors and developers. Cerutti

et al. [7] did a cross-country analysis on housing finance and were able to highlight the links between housing finance development and economic growth.

Although various studies have been conducted on different housing price bubble indices, not many works have focused on their applications, especially in the Central Asian economies[2, 3, 4, 5]. This study will fill this literature gap by constructing an overall housing price bubble index for Uzbekistan and analyzing its sub-indices that may point to the potential drivers of price fluctuations in the country's evolving real estate market.

The results of the study

The level of housing provision is one of the main indicators determining the country's well-being. In particular, effective organization of the real estate market and formation of optimal prices for representatives of different social and economic strata in the market is one of the most important tasks of the state in the social sphere. The essence and importance of housing financing has been studied by many economists. Also, the state's housing financing policy is one of the important directions of the state's socio-economic policy (policy aimed at developing construction, regulating housing relations and improving the quality of housing services, ensuring housing affordability).

Table 1

The main macroeconomic indicators of the country

Indicators	GDP (billion soums)	GDP per capita (thousand soums)	GDP growth rate (%)	Employment rate (%)	Inflation (%)	Refinancing rate	Construction cost (billion soums)	Share of construction in GDP (%)	Mortgage value (trln soums)	Share of mortgage (to GDP) (%)
2013	153311.30	5069.30	107.30	67.10	11.99	12.00	7258.20	4.73	-	-
2014	186829.50	6074.20	106.90	67.70	14.02	10.00	9098.30	4.87	-	-
2015	221350.90	7072.20	107.20	68.20	10.50	9.00	11382.60	5.14	-	-
2016	255421.90	8020.10	105.90	68.70	8.93	9.00	13148.00	5.15	-	-
2017	317476.40	9802.10	104.40	69.20	19.06	9 va 14	15228.60	4.80	2.60	0.80
2018	426641.00	12945.70	105.50	67.40	26.92	14 va 16	21958.50	5.15	4.60	1.10
2019	532712.50	15863.80	106.00	68.10	17.81	16.00	30449.90	5.72	8.00	1.50
2020	605514.90	17688.50	102.00	66.00	11.44	15.00	37334.80	6.17	9.10	1.50
2021	738425.20	21149.20	107.40	67.00	13.54	14.00	45557.40	6.17	9.80	1.30
2022	896617.90	25151.90	105.70	67.20	13.85	17.00	54286.40	6.05	14.40	1.60
2023	1066569.00	29291.40	106.00	68.00	8.77	15.00	62554.20	5.86	16.90	1.60

Source. <https://stat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika/national-accounts-2>

As can be seen from the table above, the economy of Uzbekistan is a regularly growing economy, in particular, the growth rate of the GDP averaged 5% in the last 10 years, and we can see that it has decreased in 2020 only due to the pandemic. The increase in the income of the country's population also increases their ability to cover the cost of housing financing. The rate of inflation is one of the main factors that increase the cost of long-term debt capital, but the decrease in the rate of inflation from about 13.85% to 8.77% in 2023 was an unexpected positive result. The stability of prices in the country allows to reduce risks related to inflation in the process of housing financing and, as a

result, to reduce the cost of debt capital. The fact that the total value of construction and allocated mortgage loans has a tendency to increase even during the pandemic shows how high the role and importance of these industries are as an industry that meets the primary needs of the population.

Currently, the sharp increase in demand in the real estate market is associated with a number of social and economic factors. One of the most important factors is the increase in the income of the population and the relative diversification of housing financing processes, as well as the establishment of many state subsidy programs. (Fig. 1)

Figure 1. Housing demand factors [3]

Currently, the increase in demand for housing is not only related to the need to own a residence, but also to the desire to invest capital in an investment that is a source of high income.

Income from investment in housing can be divided into 2 types:

1. Income from a positive change in housing prices
2. Annual income from housing rent

The total annual profit or loss from housing can be calculated based on the following formula:

$$UT_t = \frac{UN_t - UN_{t-1}}{UN_{t-1}} + \frac{UI_t}{UN_t}$$

where:

UN_t - current house price,

UN_{t-1} - house price in the corresponding period of the previous year,

UI_t - annual income from renting a house.

In particular, the income from rent in the capital city of our republic, Tashkent, is 5.3% higher than the rate of return on long-term foreign currency deposits. Shaykhontohur, Mirzo Ulugbek and Yakkasaray districts took the first three places in terms of income from housing.

The increase in housing prices in recent years has increased the need for effective measures to help stabilize the supply and demand for housing and to finance it. A price bubble is the result of the overestimation of real estate prices due to fundamental factors, the result of which the supply potential lags

behind the high demand for housing.

One of the main risks to the banking system of a price bubble is that when the "bubble" bursts, the market value of housing purchased through mortgage loans will fall sharply below its collateral value.

In turn, financial instability in the banking system can spread to other sectors of the economy and cause an economic recession.

The following are the main factors forming the price bubble in the real estate market:

- imbalance between demand and supply for housing;
- housing prices growing faster than the income of the population.

Imbalance between housing demand and supply. Housing units per household index is one of the important indicators for assessing the real demand for housing and the effectiveness of mortgage reforms in international practice.

The housing provision index of households is determined by the following formula:

$$HUH = \frac{H}{U}$$

where,

HUH (Housing units per household) – index of household housing provision

H – number of households

U – number of available housing units

If this index is less than one, it means that the demand for housing in the relevant area is higher than the supply, and its convergence indicates a stable balance between supply and demand and reduces the pressure to increase the price without fundamental reasons.

In 2023 and 2022, the housing units per household index in the republic is equal to 1.02, and the number of existing houses in the republic is higher than the number of households.

In recent years, as a result of the significant increase in the volume of mortgage loans and the high demands of the population, the number of available houses in the city of Tashkent has reached higher indicators than the number of families.

In order to analyze the real demand for housing in the country, the level of housing provision of families was also studied.

Table 2

Level of housing provision of households and families [9]

Areas	2020 y		2021 y		2022 y		2023 y	
	the ratio of houses to the number of families	the ratio of houses to the number of households	the ratio of houses to the number of families	the ratio of houses to the number of households	the ratio of houses to the number of families	the ratio of houses to the number of households	the ratio of houses to the number of families	the ratio of houses to the number of households
Average for the republic	0,74	0,96	0,76	1,02	0,75	1,02	0,76	1,02
Karakalpakstan R.	0,87	0,90	0,83	0,93	0,82	0,94	0,83	0,96
Andijan region	0,69	0,91	0,71	0,95	0,72	0,99	0,79	1,00
Bukhara region	0,83	1,09	0,80	1,08	0,78	1,07	0,79	1,07
Jizzakh region	0,69	0,84	0,77	0,97	0,75	0,95	0,75	0,98
Kashkadarya region	0,86	1,01	0,81	1,00	0,81	1,00	0,80	1,01
Navoi region	0,78	0,96	0,81	1,02	0,83	1,03	0,85	1,03
Namangan region	0,71	0,90	0,71	0,94	0,70	0,95	0,70	0,93
Samarkand region	0,67	0,83	0,78	1,01	0,78	1,02	0,77	1,00
Surkhandarya region	0,70	0,91	0,74	0,98	0,71	0,96	0,71	0,96
Syrdarya region	0,73	0,95	0,75	1,01	0,74	1,01	0,72	0,97
Tashkent region	0,82	1,14	0,81	1,25	0,78	1,23	0,80	1,21
Fergana region	0,65	0,89	0,72	1,04	0,71	1,02	0,63	1,00
Khorezm region	0,71	1,02	0,70	1,03	0,69	1,05	0,72	1,07
Tashkent city	0,79	1,06	0,73	1,03	0,74	1,07	0,78	1,05

Source: Institute of Macroeconomic and Regional Studies, (2023) Report on the real estate and mortgage market of Uzbekistan

According to the analysis, the index of housing provision of families in the republic is equal to 0.76.

Relatively positive values of this index were recorded in Navoi region (0.85), Republic of Karakalpakstan (0.83), Tashkent and Kashkadarya regions (0.80), while relatively low values were recorded in Fergana (0.63) and Namangan (0.70).

It can be seen from these factors that today the demand for housing in Uzbekistan is significantly higher than the available supply, and the amount of unmet demand is one of the main factors that increase the price.

Housing prices growing faster than local incomes and rents indicate a price bubble is forming in the real estate market. The term "bubble" refers to persistently overestimating the real value of assets, but its existence

cannot be proven until it bursts.

An increase in demand for housing as a result of population growth can lead to the appearance of price bubbles in periods that do not match the growth of housing supply. The low cost of borrowing in the country expands the possibilities of obtaining a mortgage loan, which leads to an increase in the demand for housing.

In order to assess the probability of a price bubble in the housing market in Uzbekistan, the "Bubble Index" was developed based on the methodology of the Union Bank of Switzerland (UBS) Global Group.

This index was determined based on the weighted average value of the following five standardized sub-indices:

- the ratio of the housing price to the average annual income (fundamental factors);
- ratio of house price to annual income from rent (fundamental factors);
- the difference between prices in the region and the country (fundamental factors);
- changes in the ratio of mortgage loans to GDP (economic factors);
- changes in the ratio of construction work to GDP (economic factors).

Figure 2. Standardized sub-indices of the bubble index [5]

The weights of the sub-indices were determined using the factor analysis recommended in the OECD Guide to Composite Indicators (2008).

Factor analysis weights the sub-indices so that they capture as much of the overall bubble risk as possible. In particular, due to the fact that fundamental factors are more important than economic factors for homeowners, these factors are given more weight.

Housing bubble index data reveal specific aspects of housing market values in different regions of the country. Fundamental factors such as the price-income ratio and the price-rent ratio, as well as economic factors such as the mortgage-GDP ratio are the basis for assessing the risk of a bubble in the real estate market, and constant monitoring of these indicators ensures the formation and stability of acceptable prices in the market. is important to ensure.

The ratio of the housing price to the average annual income (fundamental factors). The price-to-income ratio indicator, which is one of the indicators of the “bubble index”, shows how many years an employee earning an average monthly salary would have to work to buy a 2-room apartment in his area. In this case, it is assumed that the house buyer directs all of his annual income to buying a house.

Based on the average monthly salary in the regions, buying a 2-room house takes an average of 6 to 13 years. Compared to income, the most expensive 2-room houses are in Samarkand region (13 years) and Tashkent city (10 years), relatively cheaper houses are in Navoi (6 years), Khorezm (7 years), Syrdarya (7 years) regions and the Republic of Karakalpakstan. (7 years) can be purchased. The price of the cheapest 2-room apartment currently offered in Samarkand region is 5 times higher than the average annual income in the region, while the price of the most expensive 2-room apartment is 30 times higher. In Tashkent, these indicators are 6 and 26 times, respectively. For comparison, in the Khorezm region, to buy an apartment of the same category, from 4 to 13 times more than the average annual income is required.

Ratio of house price to annual income from rent (fundamental factors). Faster growth in house prices relative to rents increases the price-to-rent ratio, or conversely, faster growth in rents shortens the time it takes for rental income to fully cover the cost of buying a home. Currently, the highest average value of the price-rent ratio for a 2-room house is in the city of Tash-

kent (12 years), while the lowest average ratio is observed in the regions of Fergana (8 years) and Khorezm (8 years).

It should be noted that the price-rent ratio in Samarkand and Namangan regions is lower than the price-income ratio. This shows that the average annual income from rent in these areas is higher than the official average wage income. This trend indicates the large population in these areas and the high demand for housing rent. On the contrary, the lower price-income ratio than the price-rent ratio in Navoi, Jizzakh, and Syrdarya regions means that the average salary in these regions is higher than the income from rent.

By the end of September 2023, the average nominal salary was 7.2 million soums in the city of Tashkent, 5.8 million soums in the Navoi region and 4.4 million soums in the Tashkent region, in other regions, this indicator is in the range of 3-4 million soums.

The difference between prices in the region and the country (fundamental factors). The Institute of Macroeconomic and Regional Studies conducted a survey among 141 construction companies in 9 regions of the republic in order to study the formation of housing prices, problems and shortcomings in the field of housing construction. The survey revealed the following.

Currently, construction companies offer two different prices for houses: 1) the price before the cadastral documents are completed; 2) the price after the release of cadastral documents.

The following table shows the average prices of 1 sq. m of houses in areas with high potential for housing construction.

In areas 1 sq.m. it was determined that the price after the release of cadastral documents will increase by 19-20% on average compared to the price offered before obtaining the cadastre. In the capital, this figure is 35-39%. There is a big difference between housing prices in the regions. For example, the average minimum price before registration of cadastral documents in Tashkent city is 2.2 times higher than the average minimum price in Bukhara region, 2 times higher than the average minimum price in Surkhandarya region, and 1.5 times higher than the average minimum price in Tashkent region. Also, the average maximum price after receiving cadastral documents in the capital was 2.6 times higher than the average maximum price in Bukhara region, 3.6 times higher than the average maximum price in Surkhandarya region, and 2.4 times

higher than the average maximum price in Tashkent region.

Changes in the ratio of mortgage loans to GDP (economic factors). During 2017-2023, the share of mortgage loans in GDP increased from 3.1% to 5.5%.

Based on the demographic situation in the country and the population's demand for housing, encouraging the increase of the share of mortgage loans in GDP is important in preventing the formation of a price bubble.

In the real estate market of Uzbekistan, mortgage loans serve as a foundation for providing housing to the population and stimulating the growth of the market. The possibilities of obtaining a mortgage loan are increasing year by year. In 2017, the volume of mortgage loans allocated to the population amounted to 2.6 trillion soums and the ratio to nominal GDP was 0.8%, by 2022 these figures will be 14.4 trillion soums and 1, reached 6%.

Changes in the ratio of construction work to GDP (economic factors). Taking into account the high demand for real estate objects, it is necessary to further improve the process of financing the construction of new housing in order to support the offer corresponding to this demand. In Uzbekistan, the construction sector has been developing rapidly in recent years, in particular, in 2017-2022, an 86% growth rate was observed in this sector, and as of 2023, 6.3% of the country's GDP

is in the construction sector. The government also pays great attention to the development of the real estate industry and the attraction of foreign investments in order to ensure long-term economic stability.

As a result of state support for housing construction in 2017-2022, large-scale construction works were carried out throughout the republic. For example, preferential loans of \$500 million from the Asian Development Bank and \$300 million from the Islamic Development Bank were attracted within the framework of the affordable housing program in rural areas. Also, agreements were signed on the allocation of loans from the Asian Development Bank in the amount of \$350 million for the development of the mortgage market. As a result, construction works increased by 14.3% in 2018 and by 22.9% in 2019. Even in 2020, despite the COVID-19 pandemic, real growth in construction was 9.5% while economic growth slowed to 2%.

According to the results of the housing price bubble index, the city of Tashkent is close to the price bubble zone with an index of 1.15. This indicates that the prices are moving away from the stable level. In recent years, housing prices in the capital have grown faster than incomes and rents, and the situation in the market is being pushed towards the risk of a bubble, while construction works are "cooling" the situation due to economic factors.

Table 3

Standardized sub-indices of the bubble index in a cross-section of regions [9]

T/r	Regions	Index	Fundamental factors			Economic factors	
			Price-to-income ratio	Price-to-rent ratio	Area-to-country price ratio	Mortgage-to-GDP ratio	Construction-to-GDP ratio
1	Tashkent city	1.1	0.4756	0.6325	0.0444	0.0000	-0.0026
2	Surkhandarya	0.9	0.4278	0.4946	0.0139	-0.0010	-0.0013
3	Namangan	0.6	0.3867	0.2444	0.0019	-0.0004	-0.0010
4	Tashkent	0.6	0.3322	0.2713	0.0019	0.0005	0.0009
5	Kashkadarya	0.6	0.3630	0.2247	-0.0015	0.0003	0.0014
6	Samarkand	0.6	0.3477	0.2281	-0.0039	-0.0005	-0.0017
7	Andijan	0.5	0.2356	0.2304	-0.0007	-0.0007	-0.0018
8	Ferghana	0.4	0.2180	0.1802	0.0000	-0.0002	0.0005
9	Syr Darya	0.4	0.2179	0.1496	-0.0071	0.0001	-0.0011
10	Karakalpakstan	0.3	0.1854	0.1314	-0.0070	0.0013	0.0026
11	Bukhara	0.3	0.1819	0.1383	-0.0097	0.0000	-0.0008
12	Khorezm	0.3	0.1629	0.1422	-0.0056	0.0007	-0.0001
13	Navoi	0.2	0.1414	0.1079	-0.0143	0.0006	-0.0002
14	Jizzakh	0.2	0.1008	0.0937	-0.0122	-0.0004	-0.0020

Source: Institute of Macroeconomic and Regional Studies, (2023) Report on the real estate and mortgage market of Uzbekistan

The result of the index determined for the Surkhandarya region (0.9) indicates that housing prices in this region are significantly overestimated from their fundamental value.

Although the prices in Namangan (0.63), Tashkent (0.61), Kashkadarya (0.59) and Samarkand (0.57) regions are close to the acceptable value, they belong to the category of overestimated regions. This suggests

that there is no imminent risk of a bubble in these areas, but high prices are being observed in real estate markets, which could create potential instability in the future.

Also, the results of the index show that housing prices in provinces such as Andijan (0.46), Fergana (0.40), Syrdarya (0.36) were formed at an acceptable level compared to factors such as average incomes, rental prices, mortgage loans and construction works in these regions.

Conclusion

By researching the Housing Price Bubble Index and its sub-indices, the alarming tendency of rapid growth in housing prices is underlined. The obtained results have testified that such growth is caused not only by increasing personal consumption demand but also by the perception of the population about housing as a high-yield investment.

This will be overcome through various approaches. For instance, a more financially literate population and more lucrative alternatives to investment in the long run will help divert money from real estate. All this can also be furthered by a well-developed national financial market which will provide scope for diversified investment.

While recognizing the immediate need to address housing affordability, and hence requiring that short-run solutions should be implemented, the government could provide subsidies, target loans, and specific benefits that would bridge the housing prices and make it affordable for personal consumption. With the implementation of both short-term and long-term measures side by side, the policymakers of Uzbekistan can try to mitigate risk associated with the housing price bubble while ensuring access to affordable housing.

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